

On two asymptotic limits for demographic mortality Life Tables data

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Abstract

In an article from July 2023, the author presented a conjecture on the trend of demographic mortality as life span progresses. This earlier article provided a mathematical formulation of the statistical distribution to which mortality would tend in this case. In the present work we show that this theory predicts that the height of the mortality peak with respect to demographic age and the amplitude at mid-height of the mortality curve itself are limited to fixed values, towards which the mortality curves will tend as the lifespan increases. These limit values are also calculated numerically. These limiting requirements derive directly from the mathematical formulation of the above said conjecture. Demographic data from the United States, Japan and Italy were used as an experimental test. For the Italian case in particular, regional subdivisions were also analyzed to see if any counterexamples to the assumed limits could emerge. In all cases, the assumed limits were not exceeded by the actual data and the apparent asymptotic trend towards these limits was confirmed by the collected data. The identified height limit also gives us a quick test for future Life Tables. with 5-year age intervals: the dx data for them, in the maximum mortality interval, may not exceed 29.3 % of the total cases.

1. Introduction

In the study of demography in various countries around the world, an important role is played by Life Tables in which, among other aspects of people's life data, mortality data (i.e. the deaths of people according to various age intervals, periods of time, population groups and countries) are also presented. Indeed, the study of mortality trends and the possibility of understanding their evolution have important scientific and, of course, social significance. Many demographic studies have proposed evolutionary models of mortality and, in particular, the literature on mortality trends at older ages is extensive. It is not the purpose of this article to review these studies and models, but we can here emphasise one general feature: in all studies - to the author's knowledge - the age distribution of mortality is described through the use of two or more parameters, the values of which must be adjusted to fit the actual population curves and/or their time series (see e.g. the algorithm list table in Ref. [1]). Moreover, many of these studies are based on empirical models of the statistical distribution of mortality, as in the case of Gompertz's empirical law, derived from experimental measurements of demographic data. In the paper in Ref. [2], the author presented a conjecture on mortality at high ages in which the demographic mortality is predicted to tend toward a theoretical curve as lifespan increases. This theoretical function, called $mTC(a,TC)$, is defined by an age variable 'a' and a single parameter TC (which is proportional to the area under the curve when $0 < a < \infty$ and refers thus to "Total Cases"). This function has been analytically described and characterized in the work of Ref. [2]. The theoretical basis for the derivation of this function had been laid in Ref. [3] paper in which the Fermi statistic method was used to generate the function. The characteristic feature of our model compared to other models is that it is able to approximate the mortality curve trend with only one parameter. At the variation of TC the curve expands (or contracts) itself and shifts on the time axis (age) together with a peak of maximum mortality. The position and shape of this peak depends then only on the value of TC. Another feature of the model, first introduced in Ref. [3], is that it is not empirically derived but comes from the study of a cellular automaton - called Arbitrary Oscillator (ArbO) - which encounters stochastic 'end-of-life' events in the course of its evolution. The evolution of ArbO is described by a system

of diophantine equations (see also Ref. [4] for more information). The author’s hypothesis is that one of the solutions of this equations system can be related to real mortality curves. The specific solution of interest was calculated mathematically using the methods of Fermi’s statistical mechanics. If, therefore, real demographic mortality curves can be correlated and modelled by this theoretical function, then the same characteristic limitations of the theoretical function will have to apply to these same real curves - asymptotically over long time periods. In particular, the existing height and width limitation of the theoretical curve will also have to be observed in the real cases. In the following Section 2, the mathematical formulations of these limits will be presented. In the next Section 3 some test on the matter using the Life Tables data are carried out and finally some conclusive consideration are given.

2. The asymptotic limits of theoretical mortality curves

We recall here the basis of the analogy between the ArbO model of a cellular automaton and the demographic mortality of populations. In the course of its life cycle a single ArbO automaton has a maximum number of TC different modes at different times (i.e. ‘age’) of ending its cycle (i.e. end-of-life event - EoL). These modes are equivalent to each other and there is no preferred mode. However, the EoL mode state can be reached with a different number of ‘paths’ for each mode. Now, it is reasonable to assume that a large number (of population size) of ArbO objects, much larger than the TC, taken simultaneously, can show the statistical distribution of ArbO EoL events in a given ‘age’ interval. This ‘most probable’ distribution is represented by our mTC function and can be seen in analogy with the mortality population distribution. This distribution depends only by TC and we want to see if there are any limits to the evolution of mTC as a function of the TC parameter.

Mathematical recalls on the mTC function

Going back to the formulations of Ref. [2], let us consider the following equation that provides the mTC function, where the symbol Log indicates the natural logarithm :

$$mTC(a, TC) = -4^{a/5} (-1 + TC - \text{Log}[2])^{1 + \frac{1}{1 - \text{Log}[2]}} (-2 + \text{Log}[2]) \text{Log}[2] (-2 + 2^{a/5} + TC - 2^{a/5} \text{Log}[2])^{\frac{3 - \text{Log}[4]}{-1 + \text{Log}[2]}} \tag{1}$$

In our hypothesis, mTC represents the theoretical mortality distribution in the population vs. a sliding age interval of five years based at position ‘a’ with a given TC parameter. This continuous function is equivalent to the discrete dx figure directly given in the Life Tables with five years age intervals and should not be confused with Life Table indirectly derived quantities such as mortality rate or mortality force. An example of this function curve can be graphed as follows in Fig. 1 for the e.g. case where TC = 100000 and a is measured in years units. The graphs also show the particular a value (apeak) that leads to the curve maximum (in this case apeak ~ 88 years). In the following we will call this apeak value for brevity as ‘ap’. One can also see a slight asymmetry to the left of the curve peak, which is more evident in the logarithmic scale graph.

Fig. 1 - Linear and Log plot of the m(a,TC) as function of ‘a’ with TC=100000

This function possesses the following two remarkable properties, which come from the system of diophantine equations mentioned in Section 1:

$$\int_0^{\infty} m(a, TC) da = 5 TC; \quad \int_0^{\infty} m(a, TC) 2^{-a/5} da = 5; \quad (2)$$

Therefore, according to the first integral of (2), the area under the mTC curve depends only on the parameter TC. If we now divide the function mTC(a,TC) by TC, we will obtain a function which we will call mTCn meaning the 'normalized' function of mTC. This function will have a constant 'normalized' area under the curve.

$$\begin{aligned} mTCn(a, TC) = & \left(-4^{a/5} (-1 + TC - \text{Log}[2])^{1 + \frac{1}{1-\text{Log}[2]}} \right. \\ & \left. (-2 + \text{Log}[2]) \text{Log}[2] (-2 + 2^{a/5} + TC - 2^{a/5} \text{Log}[2])^{\frac{3-\text{Log}[4]}{-1+\text{Log}[2]}} \right) / TC; \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

TC is also decisive for finding the age 'ap' corresponding to the maximum peak of the curve and it can be shown via calculus that the following relationship holds true:

$$ap = 5 \frac{\text{Log}[2(-2 + TC)]}{\text{Log}[2]}; \quad \text{and vice-versa} \quad TC = 2 + 2^{-1 + \frac{ap}{5}}; \quad (4)$$

If we now substitute TC in (3) using the second expression in (4), we obtain via algebraic transformations a normalized mTC-type function depending by a single parameter 'ap', like:

$$\begin{aligned} mTCnp(a, ap) = & -\frac{1}{4 + 2^{ap/5}} 2^{2a/5} \left(1 + 2^{-1 + \frac{ap}{5}} - \text{Log}[2] \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\text{Log}[2]}} \\ & (-2 + \text{Log}[2]) \text{Log}[2] \left(2^{a/5} + 2^{-1 + \frac{ap}{5}} - 2^{a/5} \text{Log}[2] \right)^{\frac{3-\text{Log}[4]}{-1+\text{Log}[2]}} (2 + 2^{ap/5} - \text{Log}[4]); \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

We have thus obtained with (5) an expression of the theoretical normalized mortality curve of constant area vs the age variable and the 'ap' parameter. The (5) can then be used to mimic curves similar to the real ones present in standard Life Tables, which have by convention a death volume of 100000 cases. To obtain the comparison, it will suffice to multiply the (5) by the number 100000. This scale change is carried out in the following figure, which illustrates the different theoretical mortality curves between 15 years and 150 years for ten 'ap' values -15 years apart from each other- and with an area (i.e. number of cases) proportional to 100,000.

Fig. 2 Deaths (dx) as per mTCnp for 100000 cases and 'ap' values 15 years apart

It appears from the graphic analysis of Figure 2 that - after an initial rapid growth - the height of the peaks remains constant despite the increase in peak age (see also Table 1 in the following for numerical data). Another remarkable feature is that the apparent shape of the curves does not vary significantly and therefore their width at mid-height appears constant. The only effect of the increase in peak age (and TC) is to shift the curve itself to the right on the age axis. These considerations can be justified more formally as follows.

The height limit of the theoretical mortality curve

Considering relation (5) above, we see that the point of maximum height of the generic curve will be given by $mTCnp(ap, ap)$. It will then be possible to study its value as ap tends to infinity. It turns out from the calculations that:

$$\text{Limit} (mTCnp (ap, ap), ap \rightarrow \text{Infinity}) = -4 \frac{\text{Log} \left[\frac{\text{Log}[4]}{\text{Log}[2]} \right]}{\text{Log}[2]} (-2 + \text{Log}[2]) \text{Log}[2] (3 - \text{Log}[4])^{\frac{3-\text{Log}[4]}{-1+\text{Log}[2]}} \quad (6)$$

where the second member of (6) is an absolute number whose value is 0.292541, which then in the conventional case of the Life Tables of 100000 deaths leads to a peak limit value of 29254 cases for age intervals of five years. This limit is asymptotic for $mTCnp(ap, ap)$ although for practical purposes it is actually reached -in the theoretical curve case- by the age of about 60 years.

The full width at half maximum of the theoretical mortality curve

If, as conjectured by Ref. [2], the mortality curves are to hold up to a theoretical mTC curve as lifespan (and consequently our 'ap') increases, then it will also be interesting to assess the 'shape' of these curves to see whether they approximate the theoretical shape of the mTC. This evaluation will have to be done on a measurable basis and to this end we resort to the curve FWHM (full width at half maximum). To measure this theoretical reference FWHM, the following equation must be solved in the unknown a :

$$mTCnp(a, ap) = mTCnp(ap, ap) / 2 \quad (7)$$

In our case, the solutions can be expected to be two values, $a1$ and $a2$, with $a1 < ap < a2$ and the sought-after value of FWHM will be equal to

$$FWHM = a2 - a1$$

Unfortunately, equation (7) is transcendental in nature and therefore very difficult to solve analytically. With numerical techniques, however, it is possible to provide quite significant results as shown in Table 1 below.

Age peak year	$10^5 * mTCnp(ap,ap)$	a1 [y]	a2 [y]	FWHM [y]
15	26 718.1	6.85785	22.4807	15.6228
30	28 675.4	21.8579	37.4807	15.6228
45	29 175.8	36.8579	52.4807	15.6228
60	29 244.2	51.8579	67.4807	15.6228
75	29 252.9	66.8579	82.4807	15.6228
90	29 253.9	81.8579	97.4807	15.6228
105	29 254.1	96.8579	112.481	15.6228
120	29 254.1	111.858	127.481	15.6228
135	29 254.1	126.858	142.481	15.6228

Tab. 1 Reference limit FWHM computation

It can be seen from Tab. 1 that the FWHM appears invariant over the entire range of 'ap' values and that therefore the reference value for the FWHM to be set for the actual curves is approx. 15.6 years (for sampling intervals of five years). The second column shows the max. height of the $mTCnp$ and the asymptotic convergence to the max. value above defined. These values are consistent with the behaviour of the curves cluster seen in Fig. 2.

3. The test with the real mortality Life Tables

To test the above-mentioned boundary limits against actual demographic mortality data, we used three case studies. They refer to mortality data from three countries: the United States of America, Japan and Italy. The three countries differ in geographical location, population size and lifestyle. In the selection of these data, the distinction by sex of the population has been maintained. The demographic data were processed for the USA from the Life Tables available in Ref. [5] and [6], for Japan from Ref. [7] and in the case of Italy from Ref. [8]. In all cases, mortality tables structured 5×1 , i.e. with age intervals of 5 years referring to survey periods of one year, were considered. The period interval chosen was approximately 45 years, i.e. 1970 to 2017 for the US and 1974 to 2019 for Japan and Italy. Appendix 1 shows the data used in the females case. Thus, starting from the above-mentioned Life Tables, an additional database of correlated data was generated, including: country, sample year, maximum height of the mortality peak, FWHM of the mortality peak, age corresponding to the apex of the mortality curve, percentage share of coverage of the theoretical mTC model, all separate for the two sexes. To clarify this approach consider the examples in Fig. 3 below.

Fig. 3 Demographic mortality data (dots in (a)) are interpolated with continuous curve (b) and over-imposed on a apex compliant mTC curve (c)

The actual mortality data can be arranged on a graph with a horizontal axis corresponding to the five-year age intervals of the death cases and with the vertical axis showing the number of deaths (dx) in these intervals. In Figure 3 we represent e.g. a case of a mortality table for one country and one period (one year of sampling). It can be seen from the figure that the discrete data in the Life Tables for the chosen period (Fig.3 (a)), are interpolated by a continuous line (Fig.3 (b)). This will make it possible to calculate an equivalent maximum height and consequently determine a half-height width (FWHM) defined by the intersection segment of the interpolated curve and a horizontal half-height line. The availability of the interpolated continuous curve also makes it possible to identify the age position of the peak maximum (vertical line in Fig. 3 (c)) and thus also to draw a theoretical mTC curve having the same vertex (*). With the theoretical curve plotted in this way, it will also be possible to calculate a 'quality factor' of the mTC model as an area coverage ratio with respect to the total area of the interpolated curve, which conventionally corresponds to about 100000 cases. This factor figure is also printed in the (c) section of the figure. The numerical calculations and graphical projections were processed with the aid of a mathematical application on a computer. This tool is well known and used in science. For interested readers, the author can make the software routines used and the calculated database available. With the approach thus described, we can see below some results of the analysis of real data.

(*) The constraint assumed for the continuous curve implies a possible shift (about 2.5 years) to the right of the simulated curve with respect to the real curve. This is not critical for our analysis, as we are looking for structural effects (not influenced by an offset component) and not for an absolute age effect.

The change in the shape of mortality curves

Fig. 4, 5 and 6 show us the variation in the shape of the real mortality curves in the two extreme sampling periods and for the countries considered. In all cases, the graphs also show the limit line of maximum height for the curve defined in Section 2. Although graphs are available for all sexes, we have chosen to show hereunder the case of females, which always have a narrower FWHM than males and therefore lend themselves more to the verification of height and FWHM limits.

Fig. 4 USA females curves for 1970 and 2017 years with absolute limit line for max. height

Fig. 5 Italy females curves for 1974 and 2019 years with absolute limit line for max. height

Fig. 6 Japan females curves for 1974 and 2019 years with absolute limit line for max. height

From the figures one can see how - in the two time periods considered - in all cases there is a narrowing of the shape of the mortality peak and an approximation to the shape of the correlated theoretical peak. One also notices a more rapid coincidence between the theoretical curve and the real curve on the peak right-hand side, while on the peak left-hand side there is a greater, though diminishing, difference. This shrinkage characteristic is measured by the 'mTC Area %' figure. This effect has already been studied in Ref. [2] as part of the construction of the conjecture discussed there. The peak mortality heights and relative FWHM in the intermediate periods for the three countries and for the two different sexes were then studied in detail and the issues shown in the following.

The maximum peaks height increases with sampling period year

Fig. 7 collects the results for the peak height data analysis. It can be seen that the height of the interpolated curves increases and approaches the theoretical limit as a general trend for all the cases.

Fig. 7 Development of mortality peak height as a function of survey Life Tables years

This trend is compatible with the rise in the mortality peak age (the 'ap' magnitude) along the time periods. See Fig. 8 where also the e0 life expectancy is provided (dots values from period Life Tables). Fig. 8 shows that a general life span rise (here shown for females case) is present in the period range considered by our analysis.

Fig. 8 Development of mortality peak age and e0 (females) as a function of survey Life Tables period years

The peaks FWHM decreases with sampling period year

Similarly, the FWHM of peak mortality in the various real cases shows a decreasing trend over the sampling period. This decrease approaches the theoretical FWHM limit without exceeding it, as shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9 Development of mortality peak FWHM as a function of survey Life Tables years

The search for peaks height and FWHM in a regional case

It is now reasonable to assume that the larger the sample of data taken into account, the greater the statistical dispersion of the data can be. One might think to find counterexamples to our theory of absolute limits of mortality curves by analysing data on a reduced sample like in regional basis. This is considering that local regional data collect more internally homogeneous demographic data. Therefore, the same assessments as above were made for the specific case of regional data for a single period. This was the case of Italy where we studied the distribution of mortality data over 18 regions for the survey year 2019. The Fig. 10 and 11 shows the results obtained.

Fig. 10 Distribution of peak mortality height data for 18 Italian regions in the case of females

Fig. 11 Distribution of peak mortality FWHM data for 18 Italian regions in the case of females

In the two figures, the dashed line gives the limit value for the country total 2019. We see from the two figures above that there are regional cases where there is a greater approach (or departure) from the theoretical limits. In particular, for females in the Trentino and Marche regions, the greatest approaches to the theoretical limits are noted. For this Marche region case we show in Fig. 12 the mortality curve graph where max. height is 25640 dx (against the limit of 29254) and FWHM comes to 16.1 years (against the limit of 15.6 years) while the 'coverage' of the cases by the theoretical mTC is about 88%. Very similar data hold for Trentino region.

Fig. 12 Italy females mortality curves for year 2019 in the region Marche

4. Summary and conclusions

In Section 2 we derived from the analytical expressions of the theoretical mortality curve two absolute limits for its trend. We posed the question whether these theoretical limits are respected in real cases from demographic mortality Life Tables. In order to test our hypotheses, we measured for three countries and for 45 years interval the height and width at mid-height (FWHM) data of the curves in question by interpolating the discrete death data from the 5x1 mortality Life Tables. This, distinguishing between the data of the two sexes. The results show that, as the life span (and life expectancy e_0) increases, the maximum height and FWHM data converge towards the two respective limit levels. Values even closer to the theoretical limits are reached in two regional cases examined for Italy on 2019 data. These findings are also compatible with the author's conjecture about the tendency of mortality curves to converge towards mTC-type curves as the life span increases. In conclusion, what is presented in this paper -i.e. the possible presence of absolute limits in the mortality curves- may motivate further research and possible refinements of the ArbO theoretical model that -in particular- may lead to an understanding of the nature and explanation of the quantitative evolution of the asymmetric component on the left of the peak of the real mortality curves. The identified height limit also gives us a quick test for future Life Tables with 5-year age intervals: the dx data for them in the maximum mortality interval may not exceed 29.3 % of the total cases.

References

Author Note on References:

The literature on demographic mortality is enormous and covers a broad spectrum of scientific and social aspects. It is beyond the scope and capacity of this article to attempt to review and make reference with these studies. This choice can also be justified - in the author's opinion - by the fact that the approach illustrated here is original and not directly related to other works and research models. We will therefore only refer to works strictly instrumental to the contents of this work, leaving the correlation with other studies on the topic to the interest and experience of the reader.

- [1] A. Boulougari, K.Lundengård, M. Rančić, S.Silvestrov, S. Suleiman & B. Strass (2019) "*Application of a power-exponential function-based model to mortality rates forecasting*", Communications in Statistics: Case Studies, Data Analysis and Applications, 5:1, 3-10, DOI: 10.1080/23737484.2019.1578705
- [2] G. Alberti "*A conjecture on demographic mortality at high ages.*" <https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.10279>
- [3] G. Alberti "*Fermi statistics method applied to model macroscopic demographic data.*" <https://arxiv.org/abs/2205.12989>
- [4] Author Web Site: <https://squ-systems.eu/>
- [5] L. A. Gavrilov and N. S. Gavrilova, "*Mortality Measurement at Advanced Ages: a Study of the Social Security Administration Death Master File*", North American Actuarial Journal. 15 (3): 432–447. doi:10.1080/10920277.2011.10597629. PMC 3269912. PMID 22308064.
- [6] Elizabeth Arias and Jiaquan Xu, "*United States Life Tables, 2017*", NVSS, Volume 68, Number 7, June 24, 2019
- [7] The Japanese Mortality Database, "<https://www.ipss.go.jp/p-toukei/JMD/index-en.asp>"
- [8] Istituto Italiano di Statistica - ISTAT Web site , "[Http://dati.istat.it](http://dati.istat.it)"

Appendix 1

The following Tables are derived from data available at Ref. [5-8]

Age interv. [y]	1970	1980	1990	2003	2017
0-4	2045	1334	994	718	607
5-9	171	122	95	65	52
10-14	148	112	97	74	61
15-19	305	248	217	194	146
20-24	365	301	272	246	251
25-29	422	332	312	273	340
30-34	578	411	417	358	460
35-39	869	609	563	562	590
40-44	1304	961	811	869	796
45-49	1941	1510	1290	1267	1154
50-54	2786	2300	2051	1808	1775
55-59	3927	3346	3139	2694	2606
60-64	5441	4894	4667	4159	3566
65-69	7743	6800	6553	6001	4959
70-74	10 848	9534	9235	8633	7293
75-79	14 662	12 814	12 301	12 018	10 753
80-84	16 907	16 600	15 871	15 870	15 327
85-89	15 378	17 194	17 449	17 803	19 042
90-94	9595	12 716	14 320	15 027	17 839
95-99	3611	5935	7095	8408	9686
>100	954	1927	2251	2952	2697
Total	100 000	100 000	100 000	99 999	100 000

Table A1 - USA females mortality from 1970 to 2017 years

Age interv. [y]	1974	1979	1984	1989	1994	1999	2004	2009	2014	2019
0-4	2412	1742	1206	951	791	590	408	350	323	305
5-9	144	113	98	77	81	59	43	42	34	33
10-14	125	114	90	81	84	67	48	44	40	38
15-19	183	154	139	125	136	123	96	86	65	58
20-24	224	176	153	158	150	147	104	98	80	75
25-29	251	215	179	182	220	161	122	106	97	92
30-34	369	284	258	242	277	226	160	144	133	128
35-39	499	462	380	379	361	316	256	222	224	208
40-44	798	684	662	570	530	488	402	376	352	349
45-49	1271	1131	1011	981	829	795	668	620	581	550
50-54	1865	1778	1576	1429	1316	1178	1065	1018	906	828
55-59	3033	2583	2437	2172	1928	1783	1600	1513	1395	1322
60-64	4331	4345	3770	3408	3085	2697	2453	2327	2160	2063
65-69	6860	6461	6351	5375	4913	4439	3745	3580	3299	3124
70-74	10 825	10 375	9546	9249	7885	7280	6167	5722	5270	5000
75-79	16 790	15 818	14 897	13 451	13 604	11 735	10 410	9881	8690	8573
80-84	20 142	19 922	20 321	19 358	18 257	19 401	16 351	16 591	15 252	14 569
85-89	17 798	18 907	20 624	20 657	21 659	21 525	23 489	22 727	22 398	22 507
90-94	9557	11 251	12 428	14 844	16 353	17 830	19 820	22 284	22 334	23 485
95-99	2332	3168	3522	5492	6470	7696	9924	9947	13 000	13 014
100-104	187	310	345	785	1021	1380	2480	2182	3150	3404
105-109	4	8	9	33	49	79	187	139	215	271
110-114	0	0	0	0	1	1	3	2	3	4
115-119	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	100 000	100 001	100 002	99 999	100 000	99 996	100 001	100 001	100 001	100 000

Table A2 - Italy females mortality from 1974 to 2019 years

Age interv. [y]	1974	1979	1984	1989	1994	1999	2004	2009	2014	2019
0-4	1240	909	715	571	528	425	349	292	272	248
5-9	139	102	82	75	68	56	39	44	35	34
10-14	99	74	61	60	49	51	38	35	33	36
15-19	181	136	121	118	98	105	95	80	62	72
20-24	281	201	172	150	142	143	135	141	113	104
25-29	324	243	214	181	158	165	156	165	141	117
30-34	413	317	276	230	220	224	202	195	181	155
35-39	565	454	398	353	309	296	305	286	250	221
40-44	847	681	616	535	483	469	427	421	378	337
45-49	1260	1067	932	808	761	746	674	635	588	544
50-54	1916	1570	1381	1238	1147	1115	1042	927	883	815
55-59	2845	2338	2016	1836	1638	1593	1465	1298	1264	1168
60-64	4443	3588	3117	2696	2526	2317	2021	1830	1795	1633
65-69	7305	5816	5099	4350	3902	3611	3043	2720	2620	2466
70-74	11 709	9956	8434	7180	6438	5740	4937	4340	4070	3802
75-79	17 533	15 654	14 101	12 093	10 916	9819	8180	7485	6946	6424
80-84	20 999	20 751	20 419	19 258	17 588	15 892	13 850	12 877	12 402	11 477
85-89	17 154	19 784	21 349	22 484	22 493	21 669	20 371	20 031	19 936	19 303
90-94	8494	11 849	14 433	17 016	19 152	20 740	22 100	23 336	24 319	24 927
95-99	2033	3900	5165	7260	9188	11 473	14 842	16 393	17 195	18 767
100-104	213	575	842	1395	2016	3020	5000	5663	5764	6505
105-109	9	36	56	107	174	316	691	767	720	809
110-114	0	1	2	3	6	13	37	38	32	34
115-119	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	100 002	100 002	100 001	99 997	100 000	99 998	99 999	99 999	99 999	99 998

Table A3 - Japan females mortality from 1974 to 2019 years